

AQUAWIND

Innovative multi-use prototype combining offshore renewable energy and aquaculture in the Atlantic Basin

**WP1
SETTING LEGAL AND SOCIAL CONDITIONS**

D1.6 PROGRESS REPORT VER. 1

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Author(s)	Elba Bueno, Mónica Quesada Beatrice Avagnina, Michelle Perello, Michela Mascia	CMC CE
Reviewer(s)	Javier Roo, Antonio López Rafael Ginés Almudena Suárez Gordon Dalton, Silvia Martin, Nalu Franco Pedro Mayorga, Ana Mayorga Maria Ikhennicheu Inês Machado Alfred Mormeneo	GOBCAN-ACIISI ULPGC FCPCT PLOCAN EnerOcean Innosea WAVEC CANEXMAR

¹ PU= Public, SEN=Sensitive

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Executive summary

The aim of AquaWind is to perform a demonstration test of a multi-use (MU) integrated and co-located solution. This would consist of joining an existing marine renewable energy production Wind to Power (W2Power) prototype with an innovative finfish aquaculture solution. AquaWind joins efforts of a multidisciplinary stakeholders' consortia including R&D centres, companies, a regional authority, and a maritime cluster from three EU members states (FR, ES, PT) in the Atlantic basin. In addition to that, **AquaWind will involve a wide network of stakeholder throughout all the project phases to propitiate social acceptance.**

As detailed in the Stakeholder Engagement Plan, corresponding to deliverable D1.3, the AquaWind project aims to involve stakeholders of the quadruple helix, mainly through consultation actions, to have, at the end of the project, available data on the appreciation of this type of combined and co-located technologies.

In order to collect information from this participation, progress reports will be periodically carried out to update the status and progress of the activities with stakeholders.

The present report details, after a brief introduction, the actions carried out in AquaWind in its first 6 months of implementation, according to the stakeholder engagement plan.

Introduction

The process of stakeholder engagement is voluntary, open, and active dialog, that identifies current position of all parties included, outlines objectives and outcomes, and identifies how to achieve them.

One of AquaWind's objectives is the **implementation of an inclusive process**, by engaging stakeholders at regional, national, and European level, prioritizing public administrations, academia, business sector comprising the supply chain at local level, as well as social agents such as business associations, fishermen and civil society.

Stakeholders are being involved mainly through consultative processes, public surveys, and in some cases through sector-specific surveys (as is the case for the artisanal fisheries sector, among others). These surveys will be made available to stakeholders through an online form that will be made available to stakeholders in two rounds of consultation (one prior to the installation of the device at sea and one once the device is back on land). It has been decided to do this because, according to consultations carried out mainly on offshore wind devices, the visual and environmental impact is usually the one that raises the most doubts, even though these devices have very rigorous environmental impact assessments.

The AquaWind project has a special feature: although it involves three different countries (ES, FR and PT), the actions will be carried out mainly in Spain and specifically in the Canary Islands, so the mapping of actors has had a strong regional character. However, since the main objective of AquaWind is to carry out a demonstration test of an integrated and co-localised multi-use (MU) solution between two devices, one for wind energy generation and one for fish farming, public and private actors related to these two sectors at national and European level, with the countries participating in the project and at European level, are considered in the stakeholder involvement plan.

During the first six months of AquaWind implementation, **three main stakeholder engagement actions have been carried out**. In this case, they have not been through events directly organised by the AquaWind project, given the state of implementation of the project, as events directly organised by the project are foreseen when the project will be more advanced. However, participation in actions organised by other actors has been promoted, such as:

- The Conference on Offshore Wind Energy in the Canary Islands, Projection and Challenges, which took place on 25 October 2022 in Gran Canaria and 26 October 2022 in Tenerife, both organised by the Coastal Action Groups (Fisheries Local Action Group – FLAG) of each island.
- The XVIII National Aquaculture Congress, which took place in Cadiz and where AquaWind was presented on 23 November 2022.
- The EMFAF 2022 Info Day, which took place in Brussels on 24 November 2022.

1. Conference on Offshore Wind Energy in the Canary Islands, Projection and Challenges, which took place on 25 October 2022 in Gran Canaria and 26 October 2022 in Tenerife

Figure 1: Banner used for the dissemination of the event in Gran Canaria, where AquaWind can be found as a collaborator.

The **Gran Canaria Coastal Action Group and the Canary Islands Maritime Cluster organised a conference on 25 October 2022** to analyse the environmental impacts of offshore wind energy and its compatibility with other uses such as artisanal and recreational fishing.

The conference was opened by Alejandro Báez Acosta, Island Director of Agriculture, Livestock and Fisheries of the Island Council of Gran Canaria; Julieta Schallenberg Rodríguez, Director of Scientific Infrastructures of the ULPGC; José Joaquín Hernández Brito, Vice President of the Canary Islands Maritime Cluster and CEO of PLOCAN; Juana Ojeda García, President of the Gran Canaria Coastal Action Group. The conference was closed by Elba Bueno Cabrera, manager of the Canary Islands Maritime Cluster, and Juana Ojeda García, president of the GAC-GC.

Co-funded by
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JORNADAS “ENERGÍA EÓLICA MARINA EN CANARIAS. PROYECCIÓN Y RETOS”.

25 DE OCTUBRE DE 2022

EDIFICIO CENTRAL DEL PARQUE CIENTÍFICO-TECNOLÓGICO (POLIVALENTE 1) DE LA UNIVERSIDAD DE LAS PALMAS DE GRAN CANARIA - CAMPUS DE TAFIRA.

PROGRAMA

BLOQUE 1	
16:00/16:10	<p>Bienvenida.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - D. Alejandro Báez Acosta, Director Insular de Agricultura, Ganadería y Pesca del Cabildo Insular de Gran Canaria. - D. José Joaquín Hernández Brito, Vicepresidente del Clúster Marítimo de Canarias. - Dña. Juana Ojeda García, Presidenta del Grupo de Acción Costera de Gran Canaria.
16:10/17:30	<p>Planificación del desarrollo de la energía eólica en Canarias: planificación territorial, tipología de proyectos previstos.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planificación del Gobierno de Canarias en materia de energías renovables en especial en energía eólica marina. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - D. Gonzalo Piernavieja Izquierdo, Director de I+D+i del Instituto Tecnológico de Canarias. • Características de los proyectos de eólica marina planificados para Canarias. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - D. Tomás Romagosa, Director técnico de la Asociación Empresarial Eólica (AEE). • Necesidades energéticas en Canarias. Alternativas disponibles. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - D. Roque Calero Pérez, Dr. Ingeniero Industrial y Catedrático de Universidad en el Dpto. de Ingeniería Mecánica de la ULPGC. <p>Turno de preguntas</p>
17:30/17:50	Coffee Break

ORGANIZAN

COLABORAN

Figure 2: Programme of the Gran Canaria event, where AquaWind can be found as a collaborator (Part 1).

JORNADAS “ENERGÍA EÓLICA MARINA EN CANARIAS. PROYECCIÓN Y RETOS”.

25 DE OCTUBRE DE 2022

EDIFICIO CENTRAL DEL PARQUE CIENTÍFICO-TECNOLÓGICO (POLIVALENTE 1) DE LA UNIVERSIDAD DE LAS PALMAS DE GRAN CANARIA - CAMPUS DE TAFIRA.

BLOQUE 2	
17:50/19:00	<p>Desarrollo sostenible de energías renovables en Canarias. Impactos ambientales, compatibilidad con otros usos existentes en el territorio e investigación y desarrollo.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impactos ambientales de la energía eólica marina. Conflictos con otros usos (pesca artesanal y recreativa, turismo, etc.). - D. Manuel Ruiz de la Rosa, Director de ECOS. • Interacción de la energía eólica con las aves. - D. Yarci Acosta Santana, Delegado de SEO Birdlife en Canarias. • Investigación y desarrollo de prototipos. Plataforma AQUAWIND. - D. Javier Roo, Responsable de proyectos I+D+I (ACIISI).
19:00/19:45	Mesa de debate

Figure 3: Programme of the Gran Canaria event, where AquaWind can be found as a collaborator (Part 2).

On 25 October 2022, the Gran Canaria Coastal Action Group and the Canary Islands Maritime Cluster jointly organised an event focusing on **"Planning the development of wind energy in the Canary Islands: Territorial planning and typology of expected projects"**, with presentations by Gonzalo Piernavieja Izquierdo, Director of R&D&I of the Canary Islands Technological Institute, on this occasion representing the Regional Ministry of Ecological Transition, Fight against Climate Change and Territorial Planning of the Canary Islands Government; Tomás Romagosa Cabezudo, Technical Director of the Wind Energy Business Association; and Roque Calero Pérez, Doctor of Industrial Engineering and University Professor of Mechanical Engineering at the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria.

Another relevant aspect was the **"Sustainable development of renewable energies in the Canary Islands. Environmental impacts, compatibility with other existing uses in the territory and research and development"**, where the impact of offshore wind power and potential conflicts with other uses (artisanal and recreational fishing, tourism, etc.) were analysed, by Manuel Ruiz de la Rosa, co-founder of the company Ecos Estudios Ambientales y Oceanografía; Yarci Acosta Santana, delegate of the Spanish Ornithological Society (SEO/BirdLife) in the Canary Islands; Javier Roo, Doctor in Aquaculture and senior technician of the Canary Islands Agency for Research, Innovation and the Information Society of the Government of the Canary Islands (ACIISI) and head of international R&D&I projects of this entity.

In this session, the AquaWind project was presented by Dr Javier Roo, AquaWind Project Coordinator, who focused his speech on the research and development of prototypes, with the presentation of the AquaWind Platform, explaining that this project is the only European initiative that combines offshore renewable energy production and fish farming, in the first floating wind platform in Spain, capable of jointly producing wind energy and high quality fish, as well as simultaneously reducing the occupation of marine space. During the presentation, the survey template specifically designed for this event was distributed on paper. The event was attended by a total of 39 participants and its target audience was the artisanal fishing sector of Gran Canaria.

Once the previous blocks presentations were finished, a discussion round table was held with all the experts. Several questions were posed by the moderator, Montserrat Gimeno Ortiz, manager of the Gran Canaria Coastal Action Group, and the participating public. During the discussion, the experts talked about the importance of the Chinese and Scottish wind farms, which investments have increased substantially in the last years, risking a displacement of European presence if no faster advancements will be made in the development of this type of technology, and the importance of the offshore wind power sector, without obliterating the fishing sector that already exists, where Hernández Brito clarified that "wind power is not going to tackle the fishing sector".

There was also concern among attendees about the effect of these offshore wind power installations on birds, to which Tomás Romagosa responded that "there is a lot of equipment

being developed to avoid birds, and a project to standardize this type of equipment will be promoted". Finally, it was pointed out that combined models such as AquaWind are possible. The importance of training to work in the sector was also highlighted.

On 26 October 2022, the Tenerife Coastal Action Group organised an information and discussion day on offshore wind energy in the Canary Islands, in which the projects, the zoning, the interactions with fishing and the effects on the marine environment were discussed. This day also gave a voice to the fishing sector and the environmental sector, as well as the opportunity to open a debate with the public.

Speakers at the conference included José Antonio Valbuena, Councillor for Ecological Transition, Fight against Climate Change and Territorial Planning of the Government of the Canary Islands; Tomás Romagosa Cabezudo, Technical Director of the Wind Energy Business Association; Joaquín Gurriarán, Director of DISA Renewables; Roque Calero Pérez, Dr. Industrial Engineer and Professor of the ULPGC, Dept. of Mechanical Engineering; Yarci Acosta Santana, delegate of SEO Birdlife in the Canary Islands; and Torcuato Teixeira, Legal Advisor of the National Federation of Cofradías and Spokesperson of the Platform in Defence of Fisheries and Marine Ecosystems.

The conference was opened and closed by Javier Parrilla Gómez, President of the Tenerife Coastal Action Group, and after the presentations there was a round table discussion with a question-and-answer session for the audience.

During this day AquaWind was able to participate as a collaborator through the presence among the attendees of Elba Bueno Cabrera, manager of the Canary Islands Maritime Cluster, but did not have the opportunity to present the project or do the survey due to time constraints claimed by the organization, which will try to carry out in subsequent meetings. The meeting was recorded and is available on the YouTube channel of the organisation through the following link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=o_4SnzGtW-Y.

UNIÓN EUROPEA
Fondo Europeo Marítimo
y de Pesca (FEMF)

Gobierno de Canarias
Consejería de Agricultura,
Pesca y Desarrollo Rural

GALP
GRUPO DE ACCIÓN
COASTERA TENERIFE

Grupo de
acción costera
Tenerife

ENERGÍA EÓLICA MARINA

Jornada informativa

- PROYECTOS
- CARACTERÍSTICAS
- IMPACTOS
- INTERACCIONES CON LA PESCA

CUÁNDO:
MIÉRCOLES 26 OCTUBRE 15:30H

DÓNDE:
SALÓN TAGOROR, HOTEL ESCUELA
SANTA CRUZ DE TENERIFE

INSCRÍBETE:
GACTENERIFE@GMAIL.COM

CANARIAS
Por la transición ecológica

Fondo Europeo Marítimo y de Pesca

CMC
CONSEJO REGULADOR DE CAPANABAL

iCi

SEO
BirdLife

PARTICIPAN

Figure 4: Banner used for the dissemination of the event in Tenerife, where AquaWind can be found as a collaborator.

Grupo de acción costera Tenerife

UNIÓN EUROPEA
Fondo Europeo Marítimo y de Pesca (FEMF)

Gobierno de Canarias
Comunidad Autónoma de Canarias
Dirección General de Pesca

GALP
GRUPO ACCIÓN SOCIAL VERDE

AYUNTAMIENTO DE SANTA CRUZ DE TENERIFE

ENERGÍA EÓLICA MARINA

Jornada informativa

15:30-15:40 Bienvenida, D. Javier Parrilla Gómez, **Presidente Grupo de Acción Costera de Tenerife y Gobierno de Canarias.**

15:45-16:05 Proyectos de energía eólica marina, planificación e interacciones. D. José Antonio Valbuena, **Consejería de Transición Ecológica, Lucha contra el Cambio Climático y Planificación Territorial del Gobierno de Canarias.**

16:10-16:30 Características de la eólica marina planteada en Canarias: D. Tomás Romagosa, **Director Técnico Asociación Empresarial Eólica** y D. Joaquín Gurriarán, **Director de DISA Renovables.**

16:35-16:55 Necesidades energéticas en Canarias y formas posibles de cobertura: D. Roque Calero Pérez, **Dr. Ingeniero Industrial y Catedrático de la ULPGC, Dpto. de Ingeniería Mecánica.**

17:00-17:20 Impactos ambientales de la energía eólica marina: D. Yarci Acosta Santana, **Delegado de SEO Birdlife en Canarias.**

17:25-17:45 Eólica marina en España, proyectos en funcionamiento y el sector pesquero: D. Torcuato Teixeira, **Asesor jurídico de la Federación Nacional de Cofradías y Portavoz de la Plataforma en defensa de la Pesca y de los Ecosistemas Marinos.**

17:50-18:20 Coffee Break

18.20-19:30 Mesa debate con preguntas

19:35 Cierre: D. Javier Parrilla Gómez, **Presidente Grupo de Acción Costera Tenerife.**

CUÁNDO:
MIÉRCOLES 26 OCTUBRE 15:30H

DÓNDE:
SALÓN TAGOROR, HOTEL ESCUELA
SANTA CRUZ DE TENERIFE

INSCRÍBETE:
GACTENERIFE@GMAIL.COM

CANARIAS
Por la transición ecológica

Gobierno de Canarias

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PARTICIPAN

Figure 5: Programme of the Tenerife event, where AquaWind can be found as a collaborator.

1.1 Brief overview of the results of the survey

The survey template developed for this event can be found in Annex 1 of this document. The survey was elaborated through a previous bibliographic study on other surveys carried out in Spain and other European countries in relation to the social perception of wind energy and adapted in some cases to offshore wind.

Although the solution presented is a combined and multi-purpose solution between an energy generation equipment using the offshore wind resource, plus a fish farming cage, for the general public and the artisanal fishing sector in particular, what generates more uncertainty a priori, due to its novelty and lack of knowledge, is the energy generation prototype. Fish aquaculture is an activity with which artisanal fisheries have been coexisting for years and its policies and funds are normally managed by the same governmental bodies, with a relationship of coexistence and collaboration in most territories; however, marine wind energy represents an important novelty in the use of maritime space, which is why this type of multi-purpose prototype is so singular.

The survey conducted at this event included 37 questions, some of which were specific to the fishing sector. In order to facilitate the analysis, the questionnaire included a selection of options, with a final section for comments, in case the person completing the survey wished to include any appreciation or remark. Similarly, the survey does not include any personal data, to facilitate an honest response. In the last questions of the questionnaire, the participant is invited to know more about the AquaWind project through access to its communication channels and by offering the opportunity to participate in other events or activities of the project, indicating this willingness through contact by email or telephone with the WP7 leader, held by the Consulta Europa company.

In this event, 37 responses were obtained and some of the graphs with the data collected are included below. From the Canary Islands Maritime Cluster, as responsible for the implementation of the Stakeholder Engagement Plan, together with the rest of the partners, it has been agreed not to carry out a specific analysis by surveys, but it will be done at the end of the process and it will be included in the last progress report of this plan, since with partial information we could fall into partial analysis that could be counterproductive.

However, we can draw some general findings, such as the fact that, among those surveyed, wind energy and photovoltaic energy are considered to be the most suitable for the Canary Islands, with practically all respondents agreeing with the installation of offshore wind farms. However, it should be noted that, if these offshore wind farms were implemented, 62% of those surveyed consider that the main drawback would be the environmental impact, with 51% of those surveyed indicating that offshore wind energy does have the general support of society and 54% of those surveyed believing that photovoltaic energy is the most suitable, followed by wind energy with 38%.

Looking more closely at the small-scale fishing sector, this particular survey asked whether respondents thought that the implementation of offshore wind power would put this activity at risk, with 54% of respondents considering that it was not a risk and 81% thinking that having devices that combine energy production plus aquaculture in the same place was an advantage for the development of both sectors.

In addition, it was asked whether the way in which services such as monitoring, control and maintenance of these multi-purpose platforms are provided was known beforehand. 62% of the respondents indicated that they were not aware of these ways of providing services and 76% of the respondents indicated that the small-scale fishing sector can contribute to carrying out this type of support activities, and 89% of the respondents agreed that if they could contribute to these services, they would agree to provide them.

Figure 6: Survey results graphs from the sample conducted in the Conference on Offshore Wind Energy in the Canary Islands, Projection and Challenges, which took place on 25 October 2022 in Gran Canaria.

1.2 Photographic dossier

Below there is a photographic dossier of the event in Gran Canaria:

Figure 7: Photographic dossier of the Conference on Offshore Wind Energy in the Canary Islands, Projection and Challenges, which took place on 25 October 2022 in Gran Canaria.

Below there is a photographic dossier of the event in Tenerife:

Figure 8: Photographic dossier of the Conference on Offshore Wind Energy in the Canary Islands, Projection and Challenges, which took place on 26 October 2022 in Tenerife.

2. XVIII National Aquaculture Congress, which took place in Cadiz and where AquaWind was presented on 23 November 2022

Figure 9: Banner used for the dissemination of the XVIII National Aquaculture Congress (CNA).

The **XVIII National Aquaculture Congress (CNA)** was held from 21 to 24 November at the Palacio de Congresos in the city of Cádiz. The XVIII CNA was organised by the Spanish Aquaculture Society (SEA), in collaboration with the Faculty of Marine and Environmental Sciences of the University of Cadiz and the various institutions working in the field of aquaculture in the Bay of Cadiz: Andalusian Institute of Marine Sciences of the Higher Council for Scientific Research (ICMAN CSIC), Andalusian Aquaculture Technology Centre (CTAQUA), Centre "El Toruño" of the Andalusian Institute for Agricultural, Fisheries, Food and Ecological Production Research and Training (IFAPA) and the Andalusian Association of Marine Aquaculture Companies (ASEMA). They also had the support of the Campus of International Excellence of the Sea (CEI-MAR), a reference in maritime-marine research.

As the slogan of the XVIII CNA states: "Aquaculture, seas and rivers of opportunities", it is considered that aquaculture activity should be central to the concept of "blue growth" and should be a source of opportunities for entrepreneurship and job creation associated with this economic activity. The aim of the XVIII CNA was therefore to support this idea and to allow the results presented at the congress to contribute to consolidate it.

The congress, as usual, was a meeting and discussion place for the different agents of the aquaculture sector related to the various aspects of aquaculture (nutrition and feeding, welfare, reproduction, genetics, economics and production, facility engineering, instrumentation, and processes in aquaculture).

During the XVIII National Aquaculture Congress, the AquaWind project was presented, a pioneer in Europe in linking **offshore wind energy and the aquaculture production of marine fish on the same floating platform**. Representing this European initiative, **Javier Roo, head of R&D&I projects at the Canary Islands Agency for Research, Innovation, and the Information Society of the Canary Islands Government (ACIISI) and coordinator of the project**, focused his speech at the congress on the research and development of prototypes, with the presentation of the AquaWind platform. "It should be remembered that this is the only European initiative that combines offshore renewable energy production and fish farming, in the first floating wind platform in Spain, capable of jointly producing wind energy and high-quality fish," said Roo, who

also represented the University Institute for Research in Sustainable Aquaculture and Marine Ecosystems (IU-ECOQUA) of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC).

During his speech at the Palacio de Congresos in Cadiz, the AquaWind coordinator explained that one of the main innovations of the project will be to "evaluate in a real environment the combination of the production and use of renewable energy in the aquaculture activity of marine fish". In addition, **the project will work with two species of fish of great interest in aquaculture, the sea bream, and a new species for the diversification of marine aquaculture, the seriola (better known as lemon fish or amberjack)**, which is characterised by its high culinary value and interest, particularly in Japanese cuisine.

During the presentation of AquaWind, a QR code was made available to attendees through which they could access a Google Form to complete the specific survey for this event.

2.1 Brief overview of the results of the survey

The survey template developed for this event can be found in Annex 1 of this document. The survey was elaborated through a previous bibliographic study on other surveys carried out in Spain and other European countries in relation to the social perception of wind energy and adapted in some cases to offshore wind.

Although the solution presented is a combined and multipurpose solution between a power generation equipment through the wind resource at sea, plus a fish farming cage, for the general public and the aquaculture sector in particular, what generates more uncertainty a priori, due to its novelty and lack of knowledge, is the power generation prototype.

The survey conducted at this event included 36 questions, some of which were specific to the aquaculture sector. In order to facilitate the analysis, the questionnaire included a selection of options, with a final section for comments, in case the person filling in the survey wanted to include any appreciation or remark. Similarly, the survey does not include any personal data, to facilitate an honest response, however, a section was included in which the person completing the survey could include their contact details just in case they wanted to be informed and participate in other actions of the project. In the last questions of the questionnaire, the participant is invited to get to know the AquaWind project better by accessing its communication channels.

In this event, 29 responses were obtained and some of the graphs with the data collected are included below. From the Canary Islands Maritime Cluster, as responsible for the implementation of the Stakeholder Engagement Plan, together with the rest of the partners, it has been agreed not to carry out a specific analysis by surveys, but it will be done at the end of the process and it will be included in the last progress report of this plan, since with partial information we could fall into partial analysis that can be counterproductive.

However, we can draw some general results, highlighting that, as the event was held in Andalusia, the Canary Islands residents surveyed were only 10%.

86% of respondents concluded that they agreed with the installation of offshore wind farms, and 79% considered that this type of renewable energy will help the economic growth of their community, considering that the main drawback of the implementation of offshore wind farms is the environmental impact with 69% of the responses. Nevertheless, 69% of respondents consider that offshore wind energy does not have the general support of society.

In the aquaculture sector, this particular survey asked whether the participants thought that the implementation of this type of prototype, which combines energy generation and aquaculture, was an advantage for the development of both sectors. 90% of those surveyed agreed with this statement, and the same 90% considered that the implementation of offshore wind energy does not put the aquaculture sector at risk, and 83% believed that such implementation could improve the competitiveness of the aquaculture sector.

In addition, it was asked whether the way in which services such as monitoring, control and maintenance of these multi-purpose platforms are provided was known beforehand. 79% of the respondents indicated that they were not aware of these ways of providing services and the same 79% indicated that the aquaculture sector can contribute to carrying out this type of support activities, and 100% of the respondents agreed that if they could contribute to these services they would agree to provide them.

Figure 10: Survey results graphs from the sample conducted in the XVIII National Aquaculture Congress, which took place in Cadiz and where AquaWind was presented on 23 November 2022.

2.2 Photographic dossier

Below there is a photographic dossier of the event in Cádiz:

Figure 11: Photographic dossier of the XVIII National Aquaculture Congress, which took place in Cadiz and where AquaWind was presented on 23 November 2022.

3. EMFAF 2022 Info Day, which took place in Brussels on 24 November 2022

Figure 12: Banner of the EMFAF 2022 Info Day, which took place in Brussels on 24 November 2022.

On 24 November 2022 the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) organised the "**EMFAF 2022 Info Day**" on two new calls for proposals under the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF). The two calls were: "**Blue careers for a sustainable blue economy**" which had a budget of €7.5 million and aimed to contribute to the development of the next generation of blue skills and provide opportunities for attractive and sustainable maritime careers and "**Regional flagships projects supporting sustainable blue economy in EU sea basins**" with a budget of around €7,6 million, focused on cooperation in the EU sea basins, in particular in the Atlantic, the Black Sea, the Mediterranean, the Baltic Sea region and the EU's outermost regions, addressing six different themes: diversification of fishing activities, marine pollution, sustainable transport, maritime clusters, sustainable tourism and biotechnology.

The briefing, a hybrid event, was attended by 61 participants at the Albert Borschette Conference Centre, with 280 registered online. CINEA Director Dirk Beckers opened the day by introducing the EMFAF, while DG MARE Director General Charlina Vitcheva explained the European Commission's priorities in the different areas.

Throughout the day, speakers from CINEA and DGMARE presented Mission Ocean and detailed the application process for the calls, giving tips and tricks on how to write a successful proposal. Participants also learned how to prepare a capitalisation plan to continue the project after the end of the grant. The day ended with a networking session where B2B took place. The presentation and the recording are available on the [CINEA website](#).

The technician of the Canary Islands Maritime Cluster, Monica Quesada, attended the info day, in person, with the aim of identifying calls for new actions compatible with the AquaWind project. In addition, this type of event provides an opportunity to strengthen relations both with the representatives of the European Commission who participate in it, as well as with other agents linked to the development of the blue economy who are based in Brussels or who travel from other European countries to attend the event. The info day provided the opportunity for face-to-face meetings with agents of the quadruple helix such as: the University of Bologna, the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH), companies such as the STC Group, the University of La Coruña, the Pôle Mer Bretagne Atlantique (PMBA), the consultancy firm KVelocity; as well as establishing new contacts with the Valenciaport Foundation, the Collectivité Territoriale de Martinique, the Azores Government Delegation in Brussels, Maritime Technology Cluster FVG, as well as with different representatives of DG MARE and CINEA. The main purpose was to identify stakeholders at European level for the AquaWind project.

The programme of the info day was as follows:

- 09:30 AM - 10:30 AM CET. Registration and Welcome coffee
- 10:30 AM - 10:35 AM CET. Welcome. Vincent FAVREL, Head of Unit D3 (Sustainable Blue Economy), CINEA
- 10:35 AM - 10:45 AM CET. Introduction to CINEA. Dirk BECKERS, Executive Director CINEA
- 10:45 AM - 10:55 AM CET. Opening speech. Charlina VITCHEVA, Director General DG MARE, European Commission (tbc)
- 10:55 AM - 11:15 AM CET. EMFAF blue careers Call for Proposals. Andy KONTOUDAKIS, Policy Officer A1 (Maritime Innovation, marine knowledge, and investments), DG MARE. Sonia KARASAVVIDOU, Call Coordinator, D3 (Sustainable Blue Economy), CINEA
- 11:15 AM - 11:25 AM CET. Q&A
- 11:40 AM - 12:20 PM CET. EMFAF regional flagships call for proposals. Christos ECONOMOU, Head of Unit A3 (Sea-basin Strategies, Maritime Regional Cooperation and Maritime Security), DG MARE. Fabrice POURCEAU, Call Coordinator, D3 (Sustainable Blue Economy), CINEA.
- 12:20 PM - 12:40 PM CET. Q&A, including administration and financial aspects.
- 12:40 PM - 12:55 PM CET. The EU Mission Ocean and Waters Charter. Andreea STRACHINESCU, Head of Unit A1 (Maritime Innovation, marine knowledge, and investments), DG MARE.
- 02:00 PM - 02:10 PM CET. How to write a successful proposal: tips and tricks. Vincenzo GENTE, Programme Coordination Manager, D3 (Sustainable Blue Economy), CINEA
- 02:10 PM - 02:30 PM CET. Why is it important to think about “life after a grant” – tips for preparing a legacy (business plan). Anna KESICKA, COGEA, Synergies and clustering between maritime projects EMFF contract. Raphaela GUTTY, senior project manager, ASSESS project - Maritime Technology Cluster FVG
- 02:30 PM - 02:45 PM CET. Fostering synergies at sea basin level. DG MARE, Unit A3 (Sea-basin Strategies, Maritime Regional Cooperation and Maritime Security)

 03:00 PM - 05:00 PM CET. B2B matchmaking

3.1 Photographic dossier

Below there is a photographic dossier of the event in Brussels:

Figure 13: Photographic dossier of the EMFAF 2022 Info Day, which took place in Brussels on 24 November 2022.

Lessons learnt and next steps

One of AquaWind's objectives is the implementation of an inclusive process, by engaging stakeholders at regional, national, and European level, prioritizing public administrations, academia, business sector comprising the supply chain at local level, as well as social agents such as business associations, fishermen and civil society.

Although initially, in the formulation phase of the project, it was indicated that the stakeholder consultation would be carried out mainly online, in the implementation we have learned that depending on the event and the target group we want to address, it is necessary to adapt the surveys, both in the format in which it is carried out (online or on paper), as well as in the type and number of questions.

Currently, the number of questions we have asked is around 37 questions per survey, all of which are choice questions, so the time to complete the survey is not usually very long, less than 5 minutes, if we do not include observations. However, the battery of questions we have is much larger, more than 70 questions, based on previous studies of the perception mainly of offshore wind as an emerging sector. So, we are now entering a period of reflection that will lead us to the pre-installation survey of the offshore prototype and the number of questions it will have to contain.

Likewise, we have focused the questions of the consultation on the device that can be visualised (energy generation through the wind resource), since, as indicated above, it is the most pioneering, however AquaWind is a combined solution with aquaculture and therefore a more in-depth search for participatory processes and perception in the aquaculture sector will be carried out, in order to try to have at least 30% of the questions dedicated to this part of the combined device.

Conclusions

The process of stakeholder engagement is voluntary, open, and active dialog, that identifies current position of all parties included, outlines objectives and outcomes, and identifies how to achieve them. Once a stakeholder engagement activity is completed, it is essential to document, review and assess the engagement process, as well as the input and the feedback received from the stakeholders, which is done in this progress report.

On AquaWind project stakeholders will be approached mainly through public surveys and in some cases through sector-specific surveys (as is the case for the artisanal fisheries sector, among others).

This first progress report includes the 3 main actions linked to the implementation of the stakeholder's engagement plan, which have managed to bring AquaWind closer to sectoral agents of artisanal fisheries in the Canary Islands, aquaculture at national level in Spain, and at European level through one of the events promoted by the European Commission.

Annexes

SURVEY TEMPLATE (Conference on Offshore Wind Energy in the Canary Islands, Projection and Challenges, which took place on 25 October 2022 in Gran Canaria)

AquaWind is a groundbreaking project in the Atlantic region, which aims through a practical and disruptive demonstration of integrated solutions for the development of offshore renewable energy to design and implement a demonstration test. This will involve pairing a W2Power prototype for marine renewable energy production with an innovative fish aquaculture solution, including a custom-designed fish cage with novel netting materials, high digitalization level and species diversification.

The purpose of this questionnaire is to obtain statistical data which will be included in the project reports and no personal data will be requested.

SEX:

- Male
 Female

Age:

- Less than 25
 Between 25- 50
 More than 50

Occupational sector:

- Primary sector
 Student
 Service sector
 Construction
 Household
 Unemployed
 Retiree
 Industrial sector
 Other: _____

Resident of the Canary Islands:

- YES
 NO

What are your views on renewable energy?

- In favor
 Against

Do you know the different types of renewable energy that exist?

- YES
 NO

 What type of renewable energy do you think is the most suitable?

- Photovoltaic energy
- Wind energy
- Hydraulic energy
- Tidal energy
- Geothermal energy
- Biomass energy

 What do you think about offshore renewable energies?

- Beneficial
- Detrimental

 Do you agree with the installation of offshore wind farms in the selected areas?

- YES
- NO

 What do you think is the main drawback to the implementation of offshore wind farms?

- Visual impact
- Environmental impact
- Proximity
- Number of turbines required

 Would you support the installation of other types of renewable energy in the coastal zone and/or at sea?

- YES
- NO

 Do you know of any renewable energy companies?

- YES
- NO

 Do you believe that offshore wind energy is widely supported by society?

- YES
- NO

 Do you believe that you have the required information at hand regarding the marine renewable energy projects that are being planned in the Canary Islands?

- YES
- NO

 Are you acquainted with the relevant legislation on the implementation and development of offshore energy?

- YES
- NO

 Do you think that the implementation of this type of renewable energy on your island will contribute to the island's economic growth?

- YES
- NO

 Do you think that installing this type of energy is an advantage for your island?

- YES
 NO

 If yes, please select the one that you consider to be the major advantage:

- Economic
 Unlimited resource
 Benefits to the citizens
 Other: _____

 Do you think that this type of renewable energy will contribute significantly towards reducing dependency on fossil fuel imports and thus CO2 generation?

- YES
 NO

 In your opinion, should we use renewable energy and rely less on the other energies, such as burning fossil fuels?

- YES
 NO

 Do you know the “Roadmap for the development of offshore wind and marine energy in Spain”?

- YES
 NO

 Are you aware of the objectives of the Roadmap for the Canary Islands, as a “launching pad” for the implementation of this type of renewable energy in our islands?

- YES
 NO

 Are you aware of the EU Clean Energy for EU Islands initiative, which aims to accelerate the transition to clean energy on all EU islands?

- YES
 NO

 Are you familiar with the National Integrated Energy and Climate plan 2021-2030?

- YES
 NO

 Have you heard about the Canary Islands Marine Renewable Energy strategy developed in 2021?

- YES
 NO

 Do you think offshore wind energy is a competitive advantage when it comes to the ORs (Outermost Regions of the European Union)?

- YES
 NO

 Regarding the information available on the installation of this prototype on the PLOCAN test bed, do you think it is inadequate?

YES

NO

 As for the small-scale fishing sector, do you think that the implementation of offshore wind energy jeopardizes its activity?

YES

NO

 In your opinion, does the implementation of this type of prototype, which combines energy generation and aquaculture, represent an advantage for the development of both sectors?

YES

NO

 With reference to the previous question, do you think that such implementation can improve the competitiveness of the aquaculture sector?

YES

NO

 Are you aware of the way in which services such as monitoring, testing and maintenance are provided to these multipurpose platforms?

YES

NO

 Do you think that the small-scale fishing sector can contribute to the above-described activities?

YES

NO

 If you could help in the implementation of such activities, would you agree to carry them out?

YES

NO

 Would you like to get in touch with...?

Receive information.

Participate in activities.

Both: receive information and participate

I do not wish to be contacted.

 If you would like to be contacted, how would you like to be reached?

Website / social media

Newsletter / Newsletter to your email

By phone

WhatsApp / SMS

Other: _____

 Would you like to participate in activities/events organized in the Project such as courses, trainings, conferences, participatory meetings, interviews, surveys, etc?

Yes

No

 If you are interested in participating, please select the activities in which you would be willing to participate:

Webinar / Web seminar

Informative face-to-face meeting

Round table

Training

Surveys

Interviews

Other: _____

 If so, you can contact AQUAWIND's partners using the following contact details:

Email: info@aquawind.eu

Telephone: (+34) 828041258

We would also like to provide you with our social networks in case you wish to be updated on the results of the Project or where you can contact us:

Instagram: @aquawind_

Facebook: AquaWind Project

LinkedIn: AquaWind Project

Twitter: AquaWind Project

 Remarks (include here any comments or observation you may have):

SURVEY TEMPLATE (XVIII National Aquaculture Congress, which took place in Cadiz and where AQUAWIND was presented on 23 November 2022)

AquaWind is a groundbreaking project in the Atlantic region, which aims through a practical and disruptive demonstration of integrated solutions for the development of offshore renewable energy to design and implement a demonstration test. This will involve pairing a W2Power prototype for marine renewable energy production with an innovative fish aquaculture solution, including a custom-designed fish cage with novel netting materials, high digitalization level and species diversification.

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- NO

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 As for the aquaculture sector, do you think that the implementation of

comes to the ORs (Outermost Regions of the European Union)?

YES

NO

offshore wind energy jeopardizes its activity?

YES

 NO

 With reference to the previous question, do you think that such implementation can improve the competitiveness of the aquaculture sector?

YES

NO

 Are you aware of the way in which services such as monitoring, testing and maintenance are provided to these multipurpose platforms?

YES

NO

 Do you think that the aquaculture sector can contribute to the above-described activities?

YES

NO

 If you could help in the implementation of such activities, would you agree to carry them out?

YES

NO

 Would you like to get in touch with ...?

Receive information.

Participate in activities.

Both: receive information and participate

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This version can also be accessed online at the link:

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSeFnESDGoYr5WUIU49UOwnoRw0UjLMW6E919XkvAPKYJHfEjGw/viewform>

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

AQUAWIND

Innovative multi-use prototype combining offshore renewable energy and aquaculture in the Atlantic Basin

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